

Three biologists and a social scientist go to Yellowstone...

...They ponder whether there are any moose in the National Park.

. . .

The first, an ecologist, said: there are probably moose here because this ecosystem generally requires large herbivores to remain healthy.

The second, an evolutionary biologist, said: fossil ungulates have been discovered in this area, and I expect their moose descendants to be here.

The third, a molecular biologist, said: there are moose in the park because we had an undergrad collect some environmental DNA (eDNA) from around here, I think, and we found sequences that match the moose genome.

The social scientist looked at them bemused and said: 100% certain there are moose here. Look at the “Moose Crossing” sign.

Acknowledgements

I thank Saskia Hogenhout for contributing to writing this post. [This travel website asks the same question as our scientists.](#)

Addendum

In case you're interested, [you can buy a Moose Crossing sign for \\$24.71.](#)